

Management and productivity of farmers' boro rice

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In Bangladesh, spring (boro) rice is grown where surface or irrigation water is available. The crop is transplanted during the dry winter months of December and January and harvested during the hot spring months of April and May. In the river floodplains, irrigation is lifted by low lift pumps or by traditional swing baskets. In shallow terraced valleys and depressions with natural standing water, rice is sometimes double-transplanted as water recedes or is irrigated by low lift pumps and traditional irrigation equipment. In some

highland areas without surface water, cultivation is dependent on tube well irrigation.

In recent years, as more pumps became available for irrigation in the dry season, a shift in rice cropping patterns has been observed, from the more risky, low-yielding deepwater aus rices in winter to the high-yielding boro varieties in spring.

A crop-cut study during 1975-76 boro assessed management level and yield of five improved varieties and two local varieties grown in the BRRI project area. Five-square-meter areas were harvested from 178 fields in 19 villages. The crop was threshed, cleaned, weighed, and moisture determined. Yield was converted to tons per hectare at 14% moisture. Information on fertilizer and insect and weed control was collected from farmers.

Average NPK application was greater

on improved varieties than on local varieties. Farmers growing improved varieties used almost twice the amount of nitrogen as those growing local varieties. Most nitrogen fertilizer was applied in 3 splits: 30-40 kg as basal, 40 kg as first topdressing, and 30 kg as second topdressing.

Improved varieties outyielded local varieties (see table). Highest daily production was from IR9 and BR3. Generally, yields of improved varieties are higher in the boro season than in other seasons because of high solar radiation and low disease and pest incidence.

Most farmers did relatively good weeding, as is reflected by the weed control index at the time of harvest. About 60-70% used insecticides. Straw dry weight of IR9, Pajam, and Lathisail differed significantly from that of other varieties. ■

Management level and average yield of boro rice grown in BRRI Project area, Bangladesh, 1975-76.

Variety		Average rate of fertilizer N-P ₂ O ₅ -K ₂ O (kg/ha)	Weed control index ^a	Farmers using pesticides (%)	Straw dry weight ^b (t/ha)	Average yield ^b (t/ha)	Yield range (t/ha)	Estimated yield/day ^b (kg/ha)
IR9	8	97-99-26	2.50	67	3.8 a	4.0 a	2.5-5.9	39.8 a
Pajam	18	U4-63-27	2.20	40	3.0 a	4.4 a	2.9-6.5	34.8 a
UR3	2	88-96-43	3.00	100	2.8 b	4.1 a	3.9-4.3	39.2 a
IR8	111	88-62-37	3.07	55	2.9 b	4.1 a	1.6-7.2	32.9 a
Chandina	14	85-68-48	3.10	64	2.1 c	3.6 a	9.8-5.6	37.7 a
Muktahar	18	43-44-30	2.83	53	2.8 b	2.1 b	1.2-3.2	20.6 b
Lathisail	7	43-30-26	2.00	0	3.5 a	1.9 b	0.7-3.3	17.6 b

^a1 = excellent control, 5 = poor control. ^bIn a column, figures followed by the same letters are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Machinery development and testing

Economic use of Japanese walking-type rice transplanters in Egypt

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Two rice transplanting machines were used in a 1979-81 study comparing mechanical and hand planting. The two-row Mitsubishi MP 206 and the four-row Yanmar YP 400 transplanters are walking, handdriven types. The Japanese method of raising the seedlings in a wooden frame 370 × 114 cm containing

Table 1. Comparative yield components with direct seeding, hand, and mechanical transplanting at kafr El-Seikh, Egypt, 1979.

Planting method	Seeding rates (kg/ha)	Plant ht at harvest (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Panicle length (cm)	Branches (no./panicle)	1,000-grain wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)
<i>Direct seeding</i>							
Broadcasting	95-144	131.6	488.9	22.01	7.60	24.0	7.08
Drilled	95-144	137.4	418.2	23.65	11.50	24.0	9.2
<i>Transplanting</i>							
Farmer by hand ^a	95-144	129.5	324	22.05	9.9	24.2	6.2
Recommended by hand ^b	95-144	139.3	380.4	23.28	11.12	26.6	9.1
Mechanical ^c	36-48	140.6	503.4	25.14	12.5	25.0	10.1

^aThe distance of farmer hand transplanting between hills and rows is not fixed. ^bRecommended hand transplanting density = 20 × 20 cm. ^cMechanical transplanting density: MP 206 = 30 × 15 cm. YP 400 = 30 × 14 cm.